

An informal mathematical education project aimed at contrasting early school leaving: Potential and criticality

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High student dropout rates are a common phenomenon in the suburbs of many metropolises, even in high-income countries such as Italy. Although the factors prompting students to take this course of action are numerous, there is a need for research in mathematics education to address this phenomenon as well. An attempt can be made through informal mathematics education, as explained by the design research project focusing on students in grades 4–7 described in this work. Herein, I reflect on the potential of informal mathematics education in preventing student attrition, before presenting a case study to identify the weaknesses of a teaching experiment in terms of lack of democratic dialogue needed for the creation of a meaningful and accessible educational environment.

Introduction

According to the latest official Italian report on school drop-out rates (ISTAT, 2019), which refers to the year 2018, preceding the recent COVID-19 pandemic, 22% of adults aged 18–24 in the city of Naples were Early Leavers from Education and Training¹, compared to 14.5% and 10.6% at the national and EU level, respectively. This is a very alarming figure, reflecting the urban marginality in the large metropolises of Southern Italy, often accompanied by semi-illiteracy and hostility toward institutions (Camera dei deputati, 2000). In this particular context, failure to graduate from secondary school also increases the likelihood that young people will be approached by gangs and organized crime units, with devastating social repercussions. More generally, early school leaving is a very complex phenomenon, motivated by a range of factors that can be broadly classified as exogenous and endogenous (Morgagni, 1998). Exogenous factors are social, economic and cultural in nature, and pertain to students' family and non-family environment. On the other hand, endogenous factors relate to educational policies, but also concern the particular educational process in which the individual learner participates. Little research has been conducted on the link between early school leaving and school mathematics education. However, in a very enlightening study, at least for the Italian

¹ According to Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union, ISTAT measures school dropout rates by considering the percentage of adults aged 18–24 who have not completed secondary education and did not take part in education or training.

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context, it emerged that when a student drops-out from high secondary school, almost always in the same school year s/he failed in mathematics (Moscucci, Piccione, Rinaldi, Simoni, & Marchini, 2005). Thus, in order to focus on the prevention and contrast of early school leaving, it seems crucial to deepen and reflect on educational contexts not only from a more general pedagogical perspective, but also in the mathematics education research field.

The Proud of You project

Since 2018, my research group has been involved in projects aiming at preventing early school leaving. In particular, as a part of our Proud of You (PoY) project, we offer extra-curricular activities to primary and middle school students living in the suburbs of Naples. In 2021, the project scope was extended to students living in the city of Polistena, situated in another region of Southern Italy. PoY offers a further opportunity of learning to graders 4-7 through the school, but at the same time going beyond some of its usual practices. Indeed, PoY's strategy is the promotion of a fascinating, and thus often alternative, image of School. For this purpose, my research group and I developed a research-based design aimed at promoting a positive attitude towards mathematics (Di Martino & Zan, 2011). In some cases, we also had the opportunity to involve the teachers in professional development courses and to co-design with them the didactical activities (Carotenuto, Mellone, Sabena, & Lattaro, 2020). PoY is now in its third edition, allowing us to implement a cyclical design process of invention and revision, as is typical in design-based research (Cobb, Confrey, Di Sessa, Lehrer, & Schauble, 2003). My research group's overall research aim inside PoY is to explore how an informal mathematics education project could prevent early school leaving, hopefully with an effective and long-lasting action. As this is a highly innovative and ambitious project, some teaching experiments failed to yield the desired results, but nonetheless generated highly informative findings. Thus, in this work, focus is given to the importance of a meaningful and accessible educational environment. In this paper, I present a case study from which a lack of *dialogue* between teachers and students emerged (Alrø & Skovsmose, 2004), which runs counter to the PoY goals of democratic citizenship education.

Informal mathematics education's potential for preventing early school leaving

The research work related to PoY may be situated in the emerging field of Informal Mathematics Education (Nemirovsky, Kelton, & Civil, 2017). This study stream explores learning spaces that differ from the usual school settings and from everyday mathematics. The three main characteristics of informal mathematics education contexts are: the voluntariness of learner's participation, the fluidity of disciplinary boundaries, and the absence of traditional forms of assessment. As a result, informal mathematics education has "a unique potential to disseminate alternative images about the nature of mathematics and to realize the potential for everyone to engage with mathematics in creative and diverse ways". (Nemirovsky, Kelton, & Civil, 2017, p. 975). Taking care of students' vision of mathematics in *inclusive* environments is certainly a crucial issue in socially disadvantaged contexts such as those targeted by PoY. Here, the term "inclusive" is used in a general sense, as in the Italian educational system. By inclusive mathematics education I refer to the

An informal mathematical education project aimed at contrasting early school leaving participation in mathematical activities by individuals with claimed disabilities or with special educational needs. The latter group also includes students with very critical cultural disadvantage. In PoY, the cultural disadvantage often takes the form of limited Italian language (considered mother tongue at school) proficiency due to the exclusive use of the local dialect in everyday life outside of school, and the lack of cooperation, if not hostility towards the school, by the families.

Nevertheless, the only students' participation in informal educational contexts may not be sufficient to improve their attitude towards (school) mathematics and school in general. Indeed, projects as PoY are expensive offer brief educational experiences, while change in attitudes generally takes times. Moreover, the mathematical activities carried out within informal contexts constitute, by their nature, a significant departure from the manner in which students are taught in school. In this regard, the findings reported by Deborah Perry are highly informative, as they indicate that, even though 5–12 years old children can enjoy visits to a mathematical exhibition, they may not relate those experiences to school mathematics (Nemirovsky et al., 2017).

Thus, an effective struggle against early school leaving should aim to create the conditions for every student to develop and maintain a positive attitude towards mathematics *within the school*. Assuming a truly inclusive perspective, this means that focus should be given to tasks students perceive as *meaningful* and that makes them feel sufficiently mathematical competent, thus *accessible*. This is a very ambitious and challenging goal that requires teacher involvement. What potential does a project like PoY have for achieving this goal? Probably, one of the greatest potentialities of projects like PoY stems from the first feature of informal education spaces: the voluntary nature of the learner's participation. Indeed, being oriented to the design and creation of educational spaces in which the children participate voluntarily, an informal mathematics education project compels (more than curricular mathematical activity) teachers' educators-designers and teachers to reflect and search for significance and accessibility of the activities that they offer to learners. Furthermore, the organizational, scientific, and economic support generally offered by such projects allows teachers to experiment with new methodological approaches.

PoY teachers' training courses and educational paths

Due to the space constraints, only the main characteristics of PoY teachers' training courses and mathematics education paths are described here, but further details can be found in the article published by Carotenuto, Mellone, Sabena and Lattaro (2020). As soon as it was organizationally possible, PoY educational design work was shared with teachers. This was done in order to benefit from the teachers' professionalism and experience in their particular school, to involve and empower teachers, and to better spread the research group's vision of mathematical learning. Drawing upon embodied cognition (Radford, 2014), in PoY research-based design, movement, material, and sensory experiences were considered as central elements of the work of teachers and students in mathematical activities. These components are particularly relevant in contexts such as those targeted by PoY, given the linguistic difficulties of many learners. In particular, for the manipulative activities with artifacts we

were inspired by the pioneering work of Castelnuovo (1963). Moreover, in response to social backwardness and hostility toward institutions characterizing the communities in which PoY was conducted, mathematics education and *citizenship education* were intertwined in the program design. As a result, a pleasant epistolary meeting, even if only fictitious, was created between students and people belonging to the world of institutions and the world of culture. Moreover, many historical and naturalistic sites of the city were explored during all the project. Therefore, PoY was also a chance for the involved learners to come out from their suburbs, often lived as *ghettos*, helping them transcend their geographical and social borders.

A case study conducted to understand what went wrong

During the PoY execution, communication between teachers and students was not always consistent with the idea of meaningful and accessible educational environment. This phenomenon concerned almost exclusively few secondary school level classes, and fortunately was sporadic. Therefore, a case study of a particular conversation between a secondary teacher and a group of pupils was conducted to shed light on this critical issue, as described below.

Dialogue, absolutism, and authority in mathematics classrooms

Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) explored the role of communication in learning mathematics from a *critical mathematics education* point of view. Their perspective is particularly relevant for the PoY project, given its citizenship education component, and its goal of preventing early school leaving in socially disadvantages contexts. In fact, one of the issues of critical mathematics education is the promotion of individual empowerment through citizenship development.

Drawing upon the works of Freire (1972) and Rogers (1994), Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) described the educational *dialogue* in general terms as an “*inquiry process* which includes an exploration of participant *perspectives* as well as a willingness to suspend one’s pre-understandings – at least for a moment” (p. 15). Participating in a dialogue implies verbalizing one’s perspectives and listening and accepting those conveyed by others. However, the authors also noted that perspectives are rarely expressed in a conversation, but rather remain in the background, despite influencing interlocutors’ interpretation of what is being said by others. They also observed that a dialogue requires participants to suspend their own perspectives in order to welcome those of others and participate in a process of collective construction of new perspectives. The authors noted that such a conceptualization of dialogue necessitates that participants are willing to *run a risk* and to *maintain equality*. In the educational context, a collective inquiry process requires the teacher to share power with all students in the classroom, which can be risky, as something unexpected can happen at any time. From the point of view of students, participating in a collective inquiry means taking the control of the activities, and thus assuming the *responsibility* for its development and of what can be learned from the dialogue. This dynamic is akin to Rogers’s (1994) “person-centered” approach to learning, which not only facilitates learning and learning how to learn, but also develops student’s responsibility and their democratic citizenship competencies. Conversely, in the “traditional mode”, the teacher has the sole control of all interactions within the classroom, due to which democratic values are absent and students

An informal mathematical education project aimed at contrasting early school leaving are taught to obey those in power. As emphasized by both Freire (1972) and Rogers (1994), dialogue is a mode of analysis and a fundamental way of learning, but it is also a type of human interaction, which requires a lovely, respectful, and faithful relationship. Teachers and their students are certainly closed in an asymmetrical relationship, since they do not have the same role in the educational process. Nevertheless, in a dialogue, they are required to maintain equality, i.e., to deal with diversity and differences with *fairness*, while taking care of the emotional aspects and the diversity and differences in the content of the dialogue.

Extraneous to their idea of dialogue, but connected to the Roger's general conceptualization of traditional mode of teaching, Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) also introduced the notion of "bureaucratic absolutism" in mathematics classroom, which they defined as a system in which all mistakes, misconceptions, and alternative conceptions are to be eliminated. There, the process of eliminating errors is carried on by an "unified authority", composed by the teacher, the textbook and the answer book, which corrects errors without providing a transparent explanation to the students. In this dynamic, students could feel as clients facing a bureaucracy which refuses their application without providing any argumentation. A manifestation of classroom absolutism is the "sandwich" pattern of communication, described by Stubbs (1976) as "anything the pupil says is sandwiched in anything the teacher says" (p. 99). Conforming to this pattern, the teacher would ask a question and the student would provide a *minimal response*, which the teacher would evaluate. When adopting this approach, teachers are supposed to know in advance the answer to their questions and students are supposed to guess what the teacher expects to hear as a response. Thus, only the teacher knows the direction of communication and has full control over it, while students are concentrated in guessing, with no autonomy or responsibility for their learning process.

The phenomenon of classroom absolutism can be read in terms of *authority*; as said before, also Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) spoke about a unified authority. More recently, Wagner and Herbel-Eisenmann (2014) studied the different ways through which authority is at work in mathematics classroom discourse, focusing on pervasive speech patterns and more general indicators. They identified four authority structures—personal authority, discourse as authority, discursive inevitability, and personal latitude—which often co-occur in the same conversation. The personal latitude structure aligns with Rogers's person-centered teaching mode, as it allows all participants to make decisions (and be aware of this possibility), thus sharing authority in the classroom. Conversely, the first three categories depict different nuances of classroom absolutism, as they respectively distinguish whether authority is held by a single person (usually the teacher), whether it is attributed to the discipline of (school) mathematics, or whether it is hidden (and what is perceived in classroom is just a sense of predetermination). Teacher's personal authority can be the most pervasive structure in secondary mathematics classrooms, and the evidence that students are following the wishes of the teacher for no explicitly given reason is its general indicator (Wagner & Herbel-Eisenmann, 2014).

Context and methodology

The case study described here concerns a particular conversation between a highly motivated secondary teacher, Beatrice (pseudonym), and a group of pupils. This incident occurred during the PoY pilot phase conducted in a single school in the Naples suburbs of Scampia. The didactical paths of this pilot project were carried out from June 2018 to March 2019 and consisted of a summer camp away from school (with four morning activities related to mathematics) and an after-school educational program (comprising of eight mathematical activities organized on the school premises) for each student. The aforementioned conversation was selected because it was typical of the communication I observed between Beatrice and students.

During after-school educational program, Beatrice was involved in two didactical activities per week (involving grade 6 and grade 7 students), together with another teacher and two tutors. She conducted almost all whole-class activities, with the other teacher and the tutors taking the supporting roles. However, they shared the workload on small-group activities, which they conducted individually.

The data gathered during the PoY pilot phase consisted of initial and intermediary interviews with teachers, as well as videos and photos capturing the activities. Here, I present a fine-grained analysis of a brief transcript of a video-recording, from the point of view of the dialogical-absolutistic features and of the authority structures discussed in the previous subsection. The analysis also focused on non-verbal communication components, such as voice intonation and volume, facial expressions, gestures, and other contextual elements pertinent to participants' stances.

Analyzing a conversation between Beatrice and a group of pupils

The conversation between Beatrice and the group of students that is analyzed here took place during a didactical path aimed at exploring graphs. The students were first introduced to graphs as a phenomenon associated with body movement (by using a position sensor), after which they completed graphs and associated stories. Finally, the students interpreted choreographies conveyed through graphs and invented dances that they expressed through graphs, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: From left to right, pupils observing, manipulating, and dancing graphs, respectively.

In the group task to which the analyzed conversation pertains, the main goal was to complete a graph from which some strokes had been erased, using particular pieces of cardboard, as in a jigsaw puzzle game. Students were required to choose the pieces in

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accordance with a written narrative describing two mathematicians, Mary (Sommerville) and Hypatia, taking a particular walk. The overall atmosphere of the class appeared friendly. Below is the transcript of the selected short video excerpt, about 30 seconds long (the Italian language version is provided in the appendix). Beatrice and the three students in the group (Antonio, Brando, and Ciro) appeared very excited. From their facial expressions, postural attitudes, tones of voice, and the speed of communication, it is evident that all students (and Beatrice) were eager to complete the task.

- 1 Beatrice: What happens to the graph if I quickly move away from the sensor?
- 2 Ciro: It goes up, it goes up [he points with his right hand upwards, extending his arm as well]
- 3 Beatrice: Ok . . .
- 4 Brando: It goes above [nodding]
- 5 Antonio: At the beginning . . . [teacher interrupts with a stop gesture]
- 6 Beatrice: But if I go slowly, how does it go? [turning to Ciro]
- 7 Ciro: It goes down [he points with his finger downwards]
- 8 Antonio: Ah [he appears impatient and very eager to speak]
- 9 Beatrice: Does it go down? [addressing Ciro again with a stern voice and look]
- 10 Ciro: No, it goes straight [he makes a gesture with his hand to retract]
- 11 Beatrice: [She continues to stare at Ciro with a stern facial expression]
- 12 Antonio: Wait, wait, teacher! [speaking in dialect]
- 13 Brando: If you go near the sensor it lowers [making a downward movement with his hands], if you move away . . . [making an upward movement with one hand] [teacher interrupts]
- 14 Beatrice: Ok, then, if I go slowly . . . if I move away from the sensor slowly, as it is written here?
- 15 Ciro: It comes down [pointing with a finger downwards]
- 16 Beatrice: [She shakes her head]
- 17 Antonio: Teacher, I understood that it goes like this . . . [speaking in dialect] [He traces with his finger a zigzag line on the paper, in the missing part of the graph] [teacher interrupts]
- 18 Beatrice: No, it is a straight line, it is a straight line, it is a line [with an annoyed tone of voice and repeatedly moving the hand from left to right in a stop gesture]. It's not zzz [accompanies the sound with a gesture that recalls Antonio's zigzag line].

In this transcript, the total absence of argumentation is striking, especially considering students' incorrect answers and teachers' corrections. Moreover, although this phase of the activity was designed as group work, there was no exchange between the group members; instead, all exchanges were between the teacher and individual students, countering the PoY objective of promoting collective inquiry. Beatrice did not share power with the students in managing the task, but rather maintained full control of it, establishing a bureaucratic absolutism (Alrø & Skovsmose, 2004), in the particular form of teacher's personal authority (Wagner & Herbel-Eisenmann, 2014). This is also made evident by the fact that almost the

entire excerpt is characterized by the sandwich pattern of communication (Stubbs, 1976), which can be recognized (with small variations) in turns 1–4, in turns 6–14 (excluding turns 8 and 12), and in turns 14–16. All three line intervals begin with a (closed) question from Beatrice, which is followed by a response from one or two students, and end with Beatrice evaluating it (even with a simple head shake, as in turn 16). It can also be seen that almost all student responses to these questions were minimal. This is probably what the teacher expected, since the only longer response (turn 13) was interrupted, probably because it was anticipated by a ‘correct’ hand gesture. The fact that the students were busy guessing what the teacher was thinking, rather than taking responsibility for their learning process, is evident in turns 7–10. In turn 7, *Ciro* said “It goes down,” but in turn 10, he changed his answer to “No, it goes straight” for no apparent reason, but probably because of Beatrice’s negative evaluation in turn 9 (“Does it go down?” [addressing *Ciro* again with a stern voice and look]).

Another characteristic that made the observed communication far from being a dialogue—as conceived by Freire (1972) and Rogers (1994)—was the absence of fairness in the teacher–student relationship. From the point of view of managing difference and diversity, the lack of argumentation has already been pointed out. Thus, Beatrice did not take care to manage her students’ unanticipated responses by investigating their origins (nor did the students request explanations for the corrections they received). Even on the emotional level, however, the conversation was unfair and Antonio, the student that struggled the most with the task (as evidenced also by his use of dialect), was the most penalized. First, from the beginning, he was not allowed to participate equally with his peers. This is evident in turn 5, when he was interrupted by the teacher with a hand gesture, and in turns 8 and 12, when he unsuccessfully requested to intervene. Moreover, in the final passages of the transcript, when Antonio finally spoke up, Beatrice responded with an intervention that can be defined as censoring. Indeed, Antonio was first interrupted (turn 17), and subsequently received a very stern correction (turn 18). The latter took place through a repetition of the same words (“No, it is a straight line, it is a straight line, it is a line”), pronounced with an annoyed tone of voice, accompanied by the same stop gesture. Moreover, his previous intervention was almost ridiculed through a sound (“zzz”). Although to a lesser extent, the conversation was not fair to *Ciro* and *Brando* either. Beatrice gave *Ciro* a stern tone and look (turns 9 and 11) and, as noted above, like Antonio, *Brando* was interrupted (turn 13).

Discussion and conclusions

At the request of the project funder, both completed editions of PoY were evaluated by an external party. Based on field observations, questionnaires, and focus groups with teachers and tutors, the overall project evaluation was positive. For example, increased school attendance on the days of extra-curricular activities was recorded, and mathematics activities were highly appreciated by both students and teachers. The weaknesses that emerged from the external evaluation were mostly organizational in nature. Beyond these evaluations, as noted in this paper, a didactical weakness emerged almost unexpectedly in some teaching experiments at the secondary level. Indeed, the elements of classroom absolutism and

An informal mathematical education project aimed at contrasting early school leaving personal authority exposed through this case study run counter to the PoY goals of democratic citizenship education. In addition, they testify to an incomplete realization of the project's potential, in terms of teacher training, aimed at the creation of meaningful and accessible learning contexts that could reduce school dropout rates. This is not to say that the dialogue between educators and teachers has totally failed. Indeed, they were able to share some approaches to teaching and implement different methodologies, valuing everyone's experiences and visions. Such dialogue, however, was not always effective in developing a shared democratic vision of teaching, and in preventing some non-dialogue practices typical of the school mathematics tradition. This outcome can be attributed to the teachers' educators lack of communication capacity in the first two cycles of experimentation. Paraphrasing Freire (1972), the teachers' educators did not yet have the words to share a dialogic vision of teaching:

To exist, humanly, is to name the world, to change it. Once named, the world in its turn reappears to the namers as a problem and requires of them a new naming. Human beings are not built in silence, but in word, in work, in action-reflection. (Freire, 1972, p. 76)

Mathematics education, with the opportunity it offers to engage learners in explorative activities and problem solving, has great potential for supporting the goals of democratic education. Among the latter is education for democratic dialogue, which can only be pursued through classroom communication that is itself dialogic.

In light of the findings yielded by this study, it seems crucial that educators become more sensitive to democratic values in mathematics education and take time to reflect with teachers on the educational dialogue and to share explicitly, in words, their perspectives on the subject.

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References

- Alrø, H., & Skovsmose, O. (2004). *Dialogue and learning in mathematics education: Intention, reflection, critique*. Springer.
- Camera dei deputati (2000). Indagine conoscitiva sulla dispersione scolastica. http://leg13.camera.it/dati/leg13/lavori/stencomm/07/indag/dispersione_scolastica/2000/0119/s000r.htm
- Carotenuto, G., Mellone, M., Sabena, C., & Lattaro, P. (2020). Un progetto di educazione matematica informale per prevenire la dispersione scolastica. *Matematica, Cultura e Società, Serie 1, 5(2)*, 157–172.
- Castelnuovo, E. (1963). *Didattica della matematica*. La Nuova Italia.
- Cobb, P., Confrey, J., DiSessa, A., Lehrer, R., & Schauble, L. (2003). Design experiments in educational research. *Educational Researcher, 32(1)*, 9–13.
- Di Martino, P., & Zan, R. (2011). Attitude towards mathematics: A bridge between beliefs and emotions. *ZDM Mathematics Education, 43(4)*, 471–482.
- Freire, P. (1972). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. New York: Herder and Herder.

- ISTAT (2019). BES 2019: Il benessere equo e sostenibile in Italia. <https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/236714>
- Morgagni, E. (1998). Adolescenti e dispersione scolastica. Roma: Carocci.
- Moscucci, M., Piccione, M., Rinaldi, M. G., Simoni, S., & Marchini, C. (2005). Mathematical discomfort and school drop-out in Italy. *Proceedings of CERME 4*, 245–255.
- Nemirovsky, R., Kelton, M. L., & Civil, M. (2017). Towards a vibrant and socially significant informal mathematics education. In J. Cai (Ed.), *Compendium for Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 968–980). Reston, VA: National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
- Radford, L. (2014). Towards an embodied, cultural, and material conception of mathematics cognition. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 46(3), 349–361.
- Rogers, C. R. (1994). *Freedom to Learn* (3rd ed.). Macmillan College Publishing Company.
- Stubbs, M. (1976). *Language, Schools and Classrooms*. Methuen.
- Wagner, D., & Herbel-Eisenmann, B. (2014). Identifying authority structures in mathematics classroom discourse: A case of a teacher's early experience in a new context. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 46(6), 871–882.

Supplement: Italian language version of the transcript

- 1 Beatrice: Cosa succede al grafico se mi allontano velocemente dal sensore?
- 2 Ciro: Va sopra, va sopra [indica con la mano destra verso l'alto, stendendo anche il braccio]
- 3 Beatrice: Ok...
- 4 Brando: Va sopra [annuendo]
- 5 Antonio: All'inizio... [l'insegnante interrompe con un gesto di stop]
- 6 Beatrice: Ma se vado lentamente come va? [rivolgendosi a Ciro]
- 7 Ciro: Scende [indica con un dito verso il basso]
- 8 Antonio: Ah [si mostra impaziente e molto desideroso di intervenire]
- 9 Beatrice: Scende? [con voce e sguardo severi, rivolgendosi ancora a Ciro]
- 10 Ciro: No, va dritto [fa un gesto con la mano per ritrattare]
- 11 Beatrice: [Continua a fissare Ciro con sguardo severo]
- 12 Antonio: Aspetti, aspetti, professoressa! [in dialetto]
- 13 Brando: Se vai vicino al sensore si abbassa [compiendo con le mani un movimento verso il basso], se vai che ti allontani... [compiendo con una mano un movimento verso l'alto] [l'insegnante interrompe]
- 14 Beatrice: Ok, allora, se vado piano...mi allontano dal sensore lentamente, come sta scritto qua?
- 15 Ciro: Scende [indicando con un dito verso il basso]
- 16 Beatrice: [Fa cenno di no con il capo]
- 17 Antonio: Professoressa, ho capito quello fa così... [parlando in dialetto] [Traccia con il dito una linea a zig-zag sul foglio, nella parte mancante del grafico] [l'insegnante interrompe]
- 18 Beatrice: No, è una linea retta, è una linea retta, è una linea [con un tono di voce infastidito e muovendo ripetutamente la mano da sinistra a destra con un gesto di stop]. Non è zzz [accompagna il suono con un gesto che imita la linea a zig zag di Antonio].